

The epistemological role of archaeological typologies and the choice of archaeological methodology. Version 1

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Abstract

Classification play a key role in all disciplines and classifications influence what we can know and can learn from research. This paper first explores which role classifications play in epistemology. The different classes considered range from simple terms to complex categories. A short overview of some typologies of classifications address aspects such as natural classes versus synthetic classes, mono- versus polythetic classifications, or sharp versus fuzzy classifications. Afterwards we turn to typologies understood as interpreted classifications. While mere classifications just work with low level theories that are concerned with rather technical contents, typologies require high level theories that offer a sound basis to interpret the actual content of the types. The classical artefact types are compared with other classification levels such as features or entities that emerge from grouping artefact types (cultures etc.). In particular we consider the surplus of types in comparison with simple features. After discussing the basics of classification and typology we are well prepared to turn to the issue of choosing the right classification method. This is a particular important question because there is no "anything goes". Each method that produces different results is answering a different question and hence it is, at least if the problem is presented precisely and well possible to decide for the optimal method. Seriation, a traditional tool for developing chronologies in archaeology seems to loose importance due to scientific dating and the reasonable critique, that the input categories, types and graves for instance are problematic. Seriations using traditional typologies or even worse, the next typology at hand are a kind of blind flying through chronological evidence. Considering alternative classifications might be a much better solution and nowadays scientific dating provide the option to validate the results. Used in this way the chronologies and the typology of the best fit form the basis for social and historical interpretations of the content of the classifications. Turning around the traditional approach might open new perspectives to archaeology. The second challenge discussed in this paper will be machine learning. From a technical perspective machine learning today is a rather well developed approach, even if there is much room to improve. Much more pressing than technical improvements are questions that address the application of machine learning in epistemological work flows. Basically, machine learning learns to apply a given classification and the results can be forwarded for further analysis to generate new knowledge. Involving machine learning in a more creative way would multiply the potential of those techniques for archaeological interpretation.

Keywords: Archaeology, Epistemology, Classification, Typology, Typology of Classifications

Introduction

Classification is often derided in archaeology as a necessary evil or even a useless end in itself. Yet archaeologists, like researchers in other disciplines, continue to classify and typologise. There are good reasons for this. Without classes, no general statements can be made, and research would be deprived of its central tool. But if classification plays such an important role in the sciences, then it should be examined more closely and its potential for knowledge, as well as its limitations, should be considered more closely. Some basic questions arise. What are classes? How do they contribute to knowledge and knowledge acquisition? How do they fit into epistemology? Interdisciplinary study, mainly involving philosophy and various sub-disciplines of mathematics. Many ideas have different names in different contexts. Without attempting a comprehensive systematisation, several terms are occasionally used to indicate the references. Many terms and concepts are not consistently defined. This is not intended to be a comprehensive presentation of the various facets, but rather a general overview, so that common definitions and concepts are highlighted where they contribute to a consistent picture. It is possible to delve more deeply into individual aspects using the literature provided.

Ontological Basis and Mathematical Frame

The first thing we need to address is what objects we are looking at. This is not about archaeological objects, as we are initially looking at classification on a more allegorical level. Nor is it about the object of investigation, 'classification', which we have already specified above. Rather, it is about what things there are in our world that can be the subject of classification. This is the subject of ontology (**hofweber2023**), which we can by no means delve into, but which must be touched upon in order to lay a terminological foundation and to address some fundamental problems.

What is a thing that we take into account in our thinking? What is an object in our thinking and what is an object in the world? With all these things we want to talk about objects.

Objects can be composed, which raises the question of the smallest objects. In physics, the atom was long considered the smallest particle. Today it is the quark. However, it is obvious that atoms and quarks are not suitable as the smallest objects of thought, since a corresponding radical reductionism raises, among other things, the problem of emergence. In philosophy, the concept of the 'monad', developed primarily by Leibniz, is an alternative concept that integrates physical and cognitive components (**Garber2009**).

Another approach assumes that phenomena, i.e. appearances, are the elements of our thinking, and builds on the philosophical current of phenomenology developed primarily by Husserl (**Smith2018**). Even if we do not follow phenomenology as a whole, we must recognise the special importance of perception, since it is the only access to the external world, as Kant already explained, and since it is the basis of all empirical sciences. With the realisation that the objects of the real world, whatever they may be, are accessible only through sensory perception, a fundamental problem arises: How can individual units or objects be extracted from the continuum of perceptions, such as brightness and colour values at different viewing angles, or periodic changes in air pressure over time?

Are the individual atomic perceptual elements of brightness values etc. already a perception or just a group of these "measured values"? So how can we summarise any atomic perceptual elements into addressable perceptions? This is a physiological-psychological question and closely related to our topic of classification, but not the subject of this article, since we want to concentrate here on conscious and scientific classification. We do, however, need the perceptual units as a basis.

At this point we notice that the objects of perception, the phenomena, but also other things, are made manageable with the help of signs. This is the subject of semiotics (**Eco2010**).

We now assume that there are different objects that can be objects of thought and that can be handled with the help of signs. Now we need to establish some very basic relationships between the objects. These are identity, equality and congruence (**Felgner2020**).

The first thing to clarify is when objects are identical. This question only makes sense if it is possible for the same object to appear differently. This question is therefore always in the context of some kind of perception. A clear answer to this is provided by the so-called 'Leibniz's Law' (**forrest2020**), which was ultimately only seriously questioned by the perspective of quantum physics (**french2019**). This law states that objects should be considered identical if they do not differ in any characteristics. The decisive element here are the characteristics, which can only be used if they have been observed, i.e. are available. Since not all characteristics can be observed in empirical research in principle, the determination of identity must always be seen from the perspective of certain observations and therefore requires a context. Only in non-empirical research, such as mathematics, in which the objects can be defined, is complete knowledge of the characteristics and thus an absolute determination of identity possible.

Objects are identical or not. If they are identical, then there is only one object. At first sight, objects also seem to be either identical or not identical. But it is not quite that simple. Let us try a property based approach first. Objects are identical if they share some common property, but there is at least one property that is different. This does not mean that a clear decision has been made. How many properties must be the same for objects to be equal? And are there certain properties that must be present together? Equality can therefore only be unambiguously decided in a context in which the relevant properties are unambiguously named, or can only be progressively specified once a metric has been defined.

Leibniz used a different definition of equality, according to which two objects are equal if, in all relevant contexts, one of the objects can be replaced by the other without changing anything else (**MuellerStach2023; 6**). This version also requires a context. Leibniz also distinguishes between similarity and congruence, with congruence being given when two objects appear the same when viewed separately (**MuellerStach2023; 7**). This can be the case when geometric objects have different sizes but the same shape.

So far we have spoken of objects 'in our minds' and 'in the world', and have deliberately avoided the concept of the 'real world', because this refers to the question of realism, which we can no longer avoid. There are three components to this question. 1. is there a real world? 2. do the objects of our thinking have a counterpart in the real world? and 3. what can we know about the real world on the basis of our thinking and our observations?

There are numerous positions on these long-debated questions on the relationship of knowledge and the 'real' world [e.g. (**Ferraris2014; Gabriel2023; Glasersfeld1995; Popper2013; Reid1764**)], the extremes of which are characterised by naive realism, which assumes that our observations and thoughts provide direct access to the real world, and radical constructivism, which assumes that there is no reality and that everything is constructed. It has to be said that these two extremes, although interesting exercises or models, are inconsistent, nonsensical and mainly fuelled by polemics. But what is the right point between these extremes?

A new realism that criticises constructivism is currently replacing constructivism in philosophy (**Gabriel2023**). Although the polemics of this new direction on constructivism still seem quite refreshing (**Ferraris2014**), it

is not these polemics but more profound analyses that constitute the scientific value of the new realism (Benoist2014; Meillassoux2018). However, for our purposes the question of realism is secondary.

Now that we have used objects to discuss the things that are the elements of classifications and their basic relationships, we can move on to the mathematical concepts, which include set theory, class theory and type theory. This provides us with the basic terminology for discussing classification.

Now that we have used objects to discuss the things that are the elements of classifications and their basic relationships, we can move on to the mathematical concepts, which include set theory, class theory and type theory. Set theory was largely developed by Georg Cantor1895 in 1895, and transformed into an axiomatic system by Abraham Fraenkel and Ernst Zermelo (Zermelo1930). Since the pioneering work of the group of Nicolas Bourbaki1970, modern mathematics has been built axiomatically on set theory. Cantor defined a set as follows: "By a 'set' we mean any aggregation M of certain well-differentiated objects m of our perception or thought (called the 'elements' of M) into a whole." (Cantor1895; 481).

Although this definition is problematic because of terms like "well-differentiated" and "whole", it gives a very good idea of what sets are. A set is a collection of things, called elements, that can be identified individually. The axiomatic definition gives properties that sets must have. These include that sets are equal if all their elements are the same, or that there is a set with no elements, called an empty set. Further more, set theory provides some methods for handling sets. For example, special sets such as subsets and union sets are defined, as well as calculation rules such as de Morgan's laws.

Classes are not part of the classical axiomatic set theories but they are used sometimes in order to circumvent some paradoxes with set theory. In general classes are defined as collection of elements that share certain properties.

With set theory, we now have the second important component for classifications, alongside objects and elements. In a sense, sets are the container in which we want to group objects in the context of classification. That would be sufficient for our purposes. There are two other alternatives to set theory for the foundation of mathematics: category theory and type theory (MuellerStach2023; Marquis2023). This is not so relevant for us, but both work with notions that also occur in connection with classifications, but can have a different meaning.

Category theory uses the terms category and class. According to Muller2001, who somehow aims to integrate category and set theory, sets are combinatorial collection while classes or logical collections are an extension of a predicate. Sets, accordingly are a particular type of classes. Eilenberg1945 defines a category as an aggregate of abstract elements that are called objects and another abstract element that is called mapping of the category. In statistics, however, categories can be regarded as disjoint classes with discrete values and stored in categorical variables.

Type theory was developed to overcome some paradoxes with Freges approach to sets. Russell originally defined "A type is defined as the range of significance of a propositional function, i. e., as the collection of arguments for which the said function has values" (Russel1908; 236).

Before we look at classification, we need to clarify the relationship between classes and sets. There are different definitions for each. From what we have said so far it follows that sets can contain almost any elements, but the elements of classes must have common properties. Classes therefore seem to be special sets. This is the statistical perspective, which is somewhat contradictory to the axiomatic mathematical perspective,

in which sets are special of classes. This contradiction arises from the fact that the term 'property' can be understood in different ways. If we realise that belonging to a set is a property sufficient to define a class, then it is clear that all sets are classes. For our purposes, however, these mathematical subtleties are of little use and we adopt the statistical perspective. This view is justified because we do not use problematic sets, such as the set of all sets, and therefore many paradoxes of mathematical set theory do not arise. Furthermore, we assume that sets are arbitrary compositions of elements, which can also be defined by enumeration, and that classes are defined by common properties. These common properties are not arbitrary, but must come from the set of properties considered relevant.

Characteristics and Types of Classifications

A short overview of some typologies of classifications address aspects such as natural classes versus synthetic classes, mono- versus polythetic classifications, or sharp versus fuzzy classifications.

First, let us recognise that classifications, whether conscious or not, whether scientific or not, play a central role in our lives. Classifications allow us to make general statements based on characteristics, e.g. 'apples are edible, but deadly nightshade cherries are not'. Type A fibulae are Phase III. Classifications underlie almost all terms. The apple mentioned above includes all objects with certain properties. Without classifications we would have very few useful terms and very few meaningful statements. The often expressed displeasure with classifications and typologies can therefore hardly be directed against them, but only against their misuse. We can go one step further and say that knowledge is based on the differentiation of things (Gabriel2016; 229) and thus builds on classifications.

Classifications also play a central role in this discussion of classification, as the distinction between sets, classes and categories has already shown. In the following, we will use numerous classifications of classification concepts and features. In some cases, the classes will only be mentioned in order to expand the thematic field and in other cases we will derive conclusions from the respective classes.

General Aspects

A set of elements is given. The task of classification is to divide this basic set into subsets whose elements are more similar than the elements of the basic set. The subsets for which this is the case and which have been worked out using classification methods are called classes. A classification system is the set of subsets. Unlike the basic set, it contains not only the elements of all the subsets, but the subsets themselves and unlike the basic set, the classification system is structured.

There are different approaches to classification, which have different properties and lead to different results. In general, the set of possible classification systems for a basic set is smaller than the set of possible combinations of the same basic set. The reason for this is that all combinations that do not contain a higher similarity within the subsets should not be considered as classification systems. A set with two circles and two triangles can be divided into two subsets, each with one circle and one triangle. We do not want to consider this subdivision as a classification, at least not until we focus on other features.

We need to recognise that all possible classification systems are initially equivalent to a basic set. It is only when we define a purpose for classification with sufficient precision that the quality of the classification becomes measurable. Now we are in a position to say that one classification system fulfils the purpose better

than another, or that they all do so to the same extent.

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Of course, classifications without purpose are meaningless. So there must always be a purpose. However, this purpose is often not explicitly defined, which makes it difficult or even impossible to measure quality and thus determine a specific approach. In the next step, the requirements for the classification system can be derived from the definition of the purpose. These include the metrics and the structure of the classification. How will it be structured and how will similarity be measured?

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A classification with a specific purpose can be interpreted. I want to call an interpreted class a type. This process is by no means automatic. A classification with the purpose of chronological order must, of course, first be checked to see whether this purpose has been achieved, i.e. whether it is plausible that the classification structure reflects a chronological order. If so, and only then, can I interpret a class of this classification system as a chronological phase. Archaeological find types often contain much more complex and rarely explicitly formulated purposes. These may include chronological relevance as well as a presumed conscious identification by the original users of the artefacts.

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Classifications thus organise a set of unstructured or continuous elements, with each class having a specific meaning. The underlying data may have a complex structure and therefore support several or many classification systems. Classification systems attempt to reconstruct this structure, usually simplifying it in the process. In a sense, classes can be seen as ontological models. From the modelling perspective (Thalheim2015, Nakoinz2018), we can distinguish the development and application of a classification system. While English usually uses the term 'classification' for both, in German a distinction of 'Klassifizierung' and 'Klassierung' is quite frequent, whereby the latter exclusively refers to the application of an existing system. The later, 'Klassierung', translates to English classing.

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Next, we turn to the features, since the classifications are based on them. We can distinguish between different types of features. This is often referred to as scale levels. There are various classification systems, but the classic categorisation by Stevens1946 is still fundamental. He distinguishes between nominal, ordinal, interval and ratio scales. It is not the categorisation that is interesting here, but the observation that the different scales allow different comparisons and statistical calculations. Each level inherits from the levels below it. Nominal characteristics are also called categorical characteristics. They simply indicate categories, and colours are a common example. Here you can only determine whether two items are the same or not. The centrality measure used is mode. Ordinally scaled features are arranged in a sequence where the difference between the ranks can be very different in terms of content. A comparison of magnitudes is possible and the median is used as the central tendency. School grades are a classic example. Interval scaled characteristics contain meaningful differences and allow differences to be compared. The central tendency is the mean. Annual figures can be an example. Finally, ratio scaled characteristics allow direct comparison of values and ratios because the zero point is meaningful. Length measures are a useful example. The allowed operations are relevant to classification because they can be used to calculate similarities and differences.

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Characteristics can be scaled down, but not up. For example, an interval scaled characteristic can easily be displayed on an ordinal scale by defining size classes in ascending order. The reverse is not possible.

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Attributes are a type of feature not mentioned here. Attributes can be defined in a number of ways. The term is often used as a synonym for characteristic. Sometimes, and we follow this concept, the term attribute is applied to Boolean characteristics, i.e. characteristics that can be present or absent. Basically, these are nominal characteristics that have only two values, present or absent, true or false. Multi-valued nominal characteristics can be divided into binary characteristics, i.e. attributes, by introducing a new variable for each

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original characteristic value. Nominal characteristics are in principle disjoint, i.e. an object can belong to only one characteristic attribute. Combinations have to be considered as combinations of characteristics, i.e. the link with the individual characteristics is lost. Attributes, however, allow combinations of characteristics to be taken into account in a simple way, while preserving the corresponding relationships. Similarly, all characteristics can be transformed into attributes. As with any transformation, some information may be lost. Obviously, this is the case because we classify the properties first to obtain attributes and afterwards the objects. Since each classification is a model, a simplification and hence a loss of information may occur. In the following, we prefer to use attributes to visualise relationships because they are ultimately the simplest type of feature and therefore focus on the essentials.

Characteristics can be divided into two groups: diagnostic characteristics, which are relevant for class categorisation, and other characteristics, which are not. The latter can be used to explore new relationships based on a correlation with the defined classes. For diagnostic traits, this would often be a circular argument.

We will now discuss some basic properties of classification systems. This can sometimes lead to misunderstandings, so it is important to cover these things. In general, we expect diagnostic features to be present in all objects assigned to a particular class. This is the role of diagnostic features. We call these classifications monothetic. The idea comes from biology, where class membership is unambiguous for many features, even when individual diagnostic features are absent. If we allow for the absence of individual features, without specifying which ones might be missing because they would otherwise no longer be diagnostic, then we speak of a polythetic classification. Element 6 in table 1 belongs to class B in an polythetic classification and forms an class of its own in a monothetic one. Cluster analysis has been developed to make polythetic classifications possible (Sneath1973, 21). This concept was introduced into archaeology by Clarke (Clarke1968). However, the way in which Clarke's work is presented often leads to misunderstandings in which non-discontinuous classifications are confused with polythetic classifications.

Table 1. Mono- (A) and Polythetic classes (B).

element	class	p1	p2	p3	p4	p5
1	A	x	x	x		
2	A	x	x	x		
3	A	x	x	x		
4	B				x	x
5	B				x	x
6	B?				x	

Polythetic classifications are useful because of two reasons. First, the observations are sometimes not perfect and incomplete observations can happen. Second, simple classification models do not always meet up with the complexity of reality. Not insisting on some diagnostic properties is somehow buffering this effect.

Polythetic classifications allow less strict class assignments with simplified classification models. The next step is to question, whether each element can only be assigned to one class. If yes, we are dealing with an disjoint classification. If no, overlapping of the classes are allowed. Now, each element can belong to multiple classes. It would be nice to know to which degrees it belongs to the different classes. This idea is realised with fuzzy sets. Fuzzy cluster models (Hoeppner1999) do not assign elements to certain classes but all elements to all classes with a certain degree of belonging, the z-value (table 2). It seems that we are jeopardising the general idea of classification because we are not any more able to make general statements such as 'all items of type a date to phase 2'. To a certain degree this is true. The advantage of fuzzy clustering is that fuzzy sets

allow to map much more complex structures with rather simple classification models than crisp classifications. In order to use the fuzzy classes, we need to de-fuzzify them using a certain assignment threshold. Parts of the required operations can use the fuzzy sets with the preserved complexity and parts use the simplified de-fuzzified data to obtain interpretations and statements. The application of fuzzy classifications is shifting the complexity from the modelling of the classification system to the analysis of the fuzzy classes. This can have some advantages but also requires some efforts.

Table 2. Fuzzy classification.

element	z1	z2	z3
1	1	0	0
2	0.3	0.3	0.4
3	0.2	0.7	0.1
4	0	0.3	0.7

From a practical point of view, Kant’s classical division into synthetic and analytic on the one hand and a priori and a posteriori on the other is of utmost importance (**Kant1998**). The terminology in this paper differs from the one in epistemology, e.g. because analytic a posteriori classifications are admitted differently from analytic a posteriori judgements, and also from the authors previous publications that are even less adapted to epistemological terminology. the current terminology seems to be balanced and differentiated enough to express some relevant aspects.

The term ‘a priori’ refers to the case that a judgement or definition of a classification system in our case, is done before empirical observations are made and data are created while ‘a posteriori’ makes use of observed data. In a certain sense synthetic (for completely artificial) and analytic (for evidence based) also could be use in this way. Synthetic could also mean to create something by agglomerating elements while analytic would mean dividing something. According to (**Kant1998**) analytic refers to logical judgements that do not produce new knowledge but extract some given knowledge from the terms. Synthetic judgements in contrast combine empirical evidence with logical analysis. In this paper synthetic rather refers to something mainly based on constructing something based on some inspiration while analytic refers to a process that mainly draws on some data. Considering this meaning, we can combine the above two dichotomies in a matrix and we get four classes (table 3) that represent different types of epistemological power.

Table 3. Four classes of classifications using Kant’s terms.

type/data	a priori	a posteriori
synthetic	sc1	sc2
analytic	ac1	ac2

The four resulting types are:

- sc1: The classification system is developed without considering the actual data and creates a system by combining features and possible observations taken from mere imagination. This type of classification allows to obtain knowledge on the objects by testing the correlation of the defined classes with properties not used for developing the classification. The results are likely to be blurred and biased in comparison with the other approaches. On the other hand, imagination can provide access to completely unobserved phenomena, so that this approach has its value.

- sc2: The classification system is developed without considering the actual data in detail and creates a system by combining features and possible observations inspired by the data or parts of the data. In particular the practice of using a subset of the data to develop the classification model belongs to this type of classifications. This type of classification allows to obtain knowledge on the objects by testing the correlation of the defined classes with properties not used for developing the classification and to develop hypotheses on the relationship of the objects classes (= ontological structure) by exploring the classification structure.
- ac1: The classification system is developed without considering the actual data but some other data indicate the contingency field and logical inference, combination and division and subdivision lead to a classification system. The data used serve as a heuristic since they might be completely different from the actual data. This type of classification allows to obtain knowledge on the objects by testing the correlation of the defined classes with properties not used for developing the classification. The results might be blurred in comparison with ac2.
- ac2: The classification system is developed considering the actual data and constructs a system by dividing the set of objects into subsets based on observed features. This type of classification allows to obtain knowledge on the objects by testing the correlation of the defined classes with properties not used for developing the classification and to obtain knowledge on the relationship of the objects classes (= ontological structure) by exploring the classification structure.

This classification of classification system is based on the research practice. The result may look exactly the same but the procedure that lead to the results restricts the interpretation of the classification systems and results. We can define different classification aims:

- Learn about the ontological structure of the world by recovering patterns of natural classes and natural entities (sc2, ac2).
- Learn about ontological relationships by correlating the classes (sc2, ac2).
- Learn about the objects classified by correlating classes with other properties and generating a certain type of context (sc1, sc2, ac1, ac2).
- Discover some new phenomena (sc1)
- Guessing some relationships of objects (ac1)

We have to add, that a research process is usually an iterative process. One may start with sc1 in order to handle the data somehow and propose a research project. When possessing some data one can turn to ac1 and/or to sc2 and finally reach sc2.

The following description concentrates on the 'a priori' and 'a posteriori' classifications. We will discuss some approaches to explore the epistemological aspects. The methodological descriptions are neither complete concerning the details of the descriptions nor concerning the list of addressed approaches that is only a small part of the existing ones.

A priori Classification

A priori classifications define the classification model or structure without knowing exactly what objects are being categorised. They are based on prior knowledge of the world in general or of specific domains. The classes used here are often rather abstract and general, and implement theories that contain ontological elements. A simple example is the division of archaeological sites into burials, settlements and hoards. This categorisation is based on considerations of the use of the sites and implies a corresponding interpretation. It is also based on indicators of use, which are often not explicitly formulated. This simple tripartite division also emphasises the exemplary nature of the classification. The tripartite division can be applied well to many sites, but categories such as wayside relics or settlement burials show that the three categories do not cover everything and are not sufficiently differentiated to adequately represent all observations. Classification of the

numerous classes, which also include burials in settlements and buildings in cemeteries, as well as bridges, harbour facilities, and mines, is not always useful, however, as many classes are sometimes not filled with specific instances in the respective projects. The choice of classes depends very much on the objective of the project in which they are used. There is no universally useful classification, and transformation between classification systems is often necessary, sometimes resulting in a loss of information.

The problem of different requirements for the selectivity of the classification is often solved by a hierarchical structure. Classes are recursively divided into subclasses. An element can belong to more than one class. In a monohierarchy, an element can only belong to other parent classes, while polyhierarchies allow several parent classes. While polyhierarchies are generally more realistic, monohierarchies are often more practical. Adding up the elements of a hierarchy level in monohierarchies gives the number of objects classified here, because the classes at one level are disjoint, but this is no longer the case if the subordinate levels are organised polyhierarchically. This ultimately means that the statistical evaluation of polyhierarchical classifications can be more difficult. An example of a mono-hierarchical classification is the division of weapons into swords, spears and slingshots. A less realistic example of polyhierarchy, which should lead us to the next concept, is a classification system that distinguishes between weapons, metal and clay at the first level. At the next level we have the three categories mentioned above, with all classes belonging to two superordinate classes.

We have almost outlined a concept that combines the advantages of a mono-hierarchy with those of a multi-hierarchy: facet classification. Here several categories are defined, each of which is subdivided monohierarchically. Each element is assigned to one class in each facet. In our example we could define two facets:

- Facet F Function
 - Class F1 Weapons
 - ✱ Class F11 Swords
 - ✱ Class F12 Lances
 - ✱ Class F13 Slingshots
- Facet M Material
 - Class M1 Metal
 - Class M2 Clay

An object that can be addressed as a metal sword can therefore be classified as F11/M1 and a clay sling as F13/M2. In this example we have also introduced a notation, i.e. the names of the classes, which represents the internal structure of the classification system. Such notations are often used to refer to each class in a concise and unambiguous manner. In this case, the letters denote the facets and the numbers denote the hierarchical classes within the facets.

An advantage of facet classification is that it allows for combinations that are not explicitly formulated. In our example, a clay sword could be specified as F11/M2. In a hierarchic system, this combination of features would have to be explicitly provided for, but this is unlikely to happen as clay swords are usually not expected.

An extreme form of facet classification occurs when a combination of numerous nominal features is used to characterise elements. Obviously, the transition from unclassified to classified data is very blurred here.

In this extreme form we have a flat classification, i.e. a classification without hierarchy, which nevertheless has a high width, i.e. number of facets. Classification depth, i.e. the number of hierarchical levels, and classification width are two key figures that characterise both a classification system and an individual class assignment. The higher these two values are, the more information is contained in the class assignment, but

also in the entire classification system. The lower they are, the easier it is to analyse the classified data. 426

When designing classification systems, it is therefore important to use the possible information content as the basis for the classification structure. Hierarchical levels are often defined on the basis of individual characteristics, as such an approach is intuitive. Vessels can be divided into metal and ceramic vessels at the first level, tall and wide vessels at the second level, and vessels with steep or flat rims at the third level. In this example we use isomorphic branches, as all branches are categorised according to the same characteristics. There are several things to consider here. Obviously, it makes little sense to introduce more hierarchy levels than the number of characteristics defined. It is also important to remember that not all characteristics are sufficiently available. Characteristics that are not or hardly available can be excluded. However, the order of the characteristics is also important. Unavailable or scarcely available characteristics should never appear in the highest classification levels, because then the other characteristics are no longer addressed in a hierarchical classification. Therefore, in addition to content considerations, it may be useful to arrange the hierarchical features in descending order of assumed availability. The level up to which an element can be classified therefore indicates how much we know about it. 427
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By moving the hierarchical features to a facet, we can prevent the shielding of deeper classification features. With facets, the question of order is much less important. Facets are also a good solution for features that occur in different forms everywhere. In our last example, it would make sense to split shape and material into two facets. The cost of transforming hierarchical features into facets is a more complicated statistical analysis. 441
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These considerations lead to some guidelines for the development of a priori classification systems: 446
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- each class is defined on the basis of a well-defined feature 448
- each feature is present only at one level of the classification hierarchy 449
- the less frequently a feature is available due to the ontological structure or the data, the lower it is placed in the hierarchy 450
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- always applicable features that compete with others for a hierarchy position are moved to their own facets 452
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- define as few facets as possible 454

Let us turn to some examples. The colon classification (Ranganathan2015) is a classical example of a at least partly faceted classification. First some basic classes such as A Natural Science or B Mathematics with internal hierarchies are defined. Each item is classified according to the five facets Personality, Matter, Energy, Space and Time. 455
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How can an a priori classification contribute to knowledge gain? 459

- A priori classifications allow us to reflect on and explain our own knowledge. 460
- The classification structure does not allow insight into the ontology of this world, but is a statement about it. 461
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- Classification allows knowledge to be gained by correlating the classes with other variables. 463
- However, the classes may be suboptimal for certain correlations, as subclasses, superclasses or other combinations of characteristics that have not been predefined may show a much clearer correlation. 464
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A posteriori Classification 466

Although there are non-quantitative a posteriori classifications, including the archaeological tradition of sorting finds on the table, quantitative approaches are central here and we will focus on them. Quantitative classifications go by various names, including numerical taxonomy or cluster analysis and cover a wider 467
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range of different methods (e. g. **Everitt2011; Schmidt2022; Sneath1973**). All quantitative a posteriori classifications can, by definition, be called cluster analyses.

Cluster analysis is always a form of pattern recognition. Structures inherent in the data are extracted using statistical methods. The cluster analysis algorithms contain an abstract classification model, which is transformed into a concrete classification structure during the analysis. To a certain extent, the classification model determines which patterns are to be recognised and which structures are to be worked out accordingly. We can therefore say that the combinatorial space for classes of a given set of elements, i.e. the total set of possible classes, is limited. This is due to two factors. First, the empirical data, i.e. the properties of the elements. The properties determine which elements are more or less similar and are therefore classified more, less or not at all. Second, the classification model or algorithm, which favours or suppresses certain types of clusters. Classification models therefore define the sensitivity of the classification.

Cluster analysis works out the optimal classification structure for given elements with properties and a given classification model. This needs to be emphasised again: The best result is determined under certain conditions. However, the best result is not necessarily convincing. Therefore, it is always important to validate the classification. Validation is therefore a component of any proper cluster analysis, which includes the following points:

- a clear definition of a goal or purpose
- a description of the data to be analysed
- a classification model and algorithm derived from the purpose and justified in detail
- the implementation of the cluster analysis with the development of the specific classification structure and the assignment of classes
- the validation of the results

Furthermore, it cannot be said that different methods of cluster analysis lead to better results. In principle, there are no different classification models that lead to epistemologically equivalent results. However, there may be different algorithms that use the same classification model, i.e. different implementations of the same method. The results of analyses using different classification models may also look formally the same. However, as each classification model is in principle associated with a goal or purpose that is only marginally different, the analyses are not equivalent.

The occasional advice to analyse the data using different methods and to believe the results if they all show the same thing is obviously nonsense. Each method, each classification model, is designed to answer a different question. Often the questions are not even asked precisely enough to choose the right method. This is a major flaw in research design.

The fact that a classification does not pass (internal) validation means that there is no structure inherent in the data that can be used as a classification structure. The data then does not suggest a specific ontology and ontological statements are not possible. Nevertheless, the classification can be used to analyse correlations with other parameters. Of course, it is not easy to interpret the correlations in this case, but it is possible to gain knowledge.

Obviously, the similarity of the elements plays a special role in the classification. Mathematically, similarities are inverse distances. So how do we measure distances in feature space? Mathematically, distances are obtained using norms derived from metrics. There are many metrics and distance measures. Among the hundreds of distance measures, the Euclidean distance, the Manhattan distance, the Jaccard distance and the Gower distance are worth mentioning. Three aspects are important when choosing a suitable distance measure: the scale level of the variables, the combination of variables and the objective. Not all distance measures

can be used for all scale levels, as the scale levels allow only certain mathematical operations to interpret distances. Even if there is a clear definition of a distance for individual variables of a certain scale, for example for interval-scaled variables in the number space of rational numbers, the distance is not necessarily given for a multivariate feature space. For example, the merging of univariate distances is done very differently for the Euclidean distance and the Manhattan distance. After all, different distance measures emphasise different aspects, and this - let's call it distortion - has to be adapted to the objective.

Distances are often given in the form of distance matrices in which the elements can be found in both the columns and the rows and the distance values in the matrix cells, so that we have self-references on the diagonal. Such distance matrices are used for grouping in the cluster algorithms.

Different approaches can be used here. The most important types of cluster analysis are hierarchical, partitioning and density-based cluster analysis (**Schmidt2022**). Other methods, such as biclustering or graph-theoretical approaches, will not be discussed in this article.

Hierarchical cluster analysis extracts a hierarchical structure of classes from the data. Many clusters are generated, which are arranged in a hierarchical structure represented in a dendrogram. A distinction is made between divisive and agglomerative methods, the latter being more common.

In divisive methods, such as Diana (**Kaufman1990**), the cluster of all elements is successively divided into a main group and a splinter group. The core of the split group is formed by the element that is, on average, furthest away from the other elements in the cluster. The elements closer to this core are assigned to the splitter group, all others to the remaining main group. For the next splitting step, the cluster with the largest diameter, i.e. the maximum distance between two elements, is selected. This continues until all terminal clusters consist of only one element. The basic idea of divisive cluster analysis is to ultimately form two subgroups that are as far apart as possible. The Diana algorithm focuses on separating outliers and elements close to them.

Agglomerative hierarchical cluster analysis, on the other hand, is based on the individual elements merging with other elements or existing clusters until only one cluster remains. The elements or clusters are merged step by step, joining the two elements, two clusters or a combination with the smallest distance between them. This is easy for elements. However, when considering one or two clusters, it is no longer obvious which distance should be taken into account. This is where the different methods of agglomerative hierarchical cluster analysis differ. The different definitions of distances mean that the methods preferentially construct certain types of clusters and are therefore particularly sensitive to these structures.

The single linkage cluster analysis takes into account the smallest distance between two elements of the two clusters under consideration. These may also be the outliers that lie in the data space in the direction of the other cluster under consideration. Accordingly, the single linkage cluster analysis tends to detect linked structures and tends to generate chain-like clusters. It is particularly sensitive to outliers. If we expect compact clusters, this method is obviously inappropriate. Full linkage cluster analysis does the opposite, taking the maximum distance into account. This results in rather small and compact clusters. Outliers also have a large influence on these methods, as the clusters are represented by elements that are as far away from the cluster centre as possible in the data space. This can be avoided by using an average of all distances in average linkage cluster analysis. However, an average of all pairwise distances between two clusters must be formed from the distance matrix. Alternatively, a representative element can be selected from the cluster, namely the element in the middle of the pairwise distance ranking. This is the median method. Here the cluster is represented by a prototypical element. This method is therefore particularly suitable if we want to

assume prototypes, i.e. ideal representatives for all clusters. If this is not the case, and we would rather say that the cluster emerges as a new entity from the merging of subordinate elements and represents a new ontological level that cannot be represented by an existing prototype, then the centroid method is the best approach. Here, a centre is calculated from the variables of the cluster elements, which represents the cluster and is used for the distance calculations. With this method, the distances have to be recalculated after each fusion. The distance of the centroids can also differ significantly from the mean distances of the elements. In the case of elements grouped laterally around the cluster centre, but leaving the central area free, the mean distance can be greater than the distance of the centroids. In addition, the maximum distance between sub-cluster centres may be greater than the distance between the new cluster and another cluster. In this case there will be undercuts in the dendrogram, i.e. the phenomenon of higher level clusters merging at a lower distance. This is not an error, but results from the particular configuration of the data and shows a certain inhomogeneity of the clusters.

In summary, hierarchical cluster analysis is an excellent tool for exploring the internal structures of data. The different methods are particularly sensitive to certain structures. A large number of non-disjoint clusters are created because the clusters are only disjoint at one hierarchical level. For this reason, a cut through the dendrogram is often made to extract a certain number of disjoint groups. Since the clusters at each hierarchical level are largely calculated without considering the other groups at that level, the group distribution at each level is sometimes suboptimal. A flat classification structure can therefore be derived from a hierarchical classification structure, but since an optimal hierarchical structure is computed, the flat structure, which is only one component of the hierarchy, does not necessarily have to be optimal.

Since the distances that lead to a fusion are usually not only due to a specific feature, the hierarchical structures constructed with these methods are not directly comparable to the a priori hierarchical classifications discussed above and are much more difficult to interpret. The clusters are ultimately not defined by the presence or absence of certain attributes, even when attributes are used as input data, but by distances in feature space. The clusters of hierarchical cluster analysis can of course be in the sense that the inherent structure of the data results from the observations. This could give the clusters their own ontological value. However, they are not natural in the sense that they could be described as a simple list of diagnostic features.

The partitioning cluster analysis does not construct a hierarchy, but a flat structure, a simple set of disjoint classes. For a given number of clusters, an optimal classification structure and assignment of elements is determined. As this sentence suggests, the problem consists of two components: first, the optimal localisation of the cluster centres in the feature space, and second, the optimal assignment of the elements to the clusters. Classical methods include k-means and the k-medoids (PAM) algorithm (**Kaufman1990**). In the k-means method, the clusters are represented by an average of the features of the cluster elements, whereas in the k-medoids method, an element represents the cluster. K-medoids is therefore based on prototypes. A k-means algorithm works by first randomly dividing the elements into k clusters and calculating the mean of the clusters in the data space. The elements are then reassigned to the clusters, choosing the cluster that increases its variance the least as a result of inclusion. The centres are calculated again and the elements are reassigned. This iterative process continues until the cluster solution does not change. Since, depending on the initial structure, a stable solution may emerge that is not the optimum, this process is repeated several times. In principle, this process leads to an optimal solution, where the quality of the clusters is measured by their variance, i.e. compactness.

The interpretation of these clusters is basically the same as for hierarchical cluster analysis. Clusters are ultimately defined by distances and not by sets of diagnostic features. However, a hierarchical structure can be derived from a flat classification using decision trees in which each node is decided on the basis of a fea-

ture. These solutions are easier to interpret and are essentially a priori classifications. However, there is no guarantee that a cluster solution will also have a clear decision tree. In any case, decision trees can be used to explore the feature structure of cluster solutions. An advantage of decision trees is that they allow to work out the minimum diagnostic set of features and thus to make a fairly reliable prediction of the class assignment from only a few features.

Complex and intertwined clusters in feature space are difficult to reconstruct using these methods. Density-based cluster analysis can help here. Unlike the distance-based methods mentioned above, they are not based on the distances between elements and clusters, but on the density values in the feature space. The density of the cluster centres is high and the clusters are separated by areas of low density. This makes it possible to extract clusters that have any shape in feature space but are connected. DBSCAN is the best known density based clustering method (**Sander1998**).

Density based clusters have neither a representative element nor a representative centre. Yes, the centre in the sense of a mean value can be outside the cluster. The decision to use a density-based method is often made on a practical level, i.e. when the distance-based methods fail to produce the desired clusters. In principle, however, this decision should be made at a theoretical level. The question is not how nice the clusters produced by an analysis are, but how well the desired structure matches the sensitivity of the method. For example, if our theory considers spirals in feature space to be possible, then a density-based method is preferable to a distance-based method. However, if the cluster structures are to be compact, or if we assume either an ideal type (k-means) or a prototype (k-medoid), then the distance-based methods are to be preferred. If the question implies a cluster structure, but the analysis is sensitive to a different structure, then the question cannot be answered with the corresponding analysis.

It should be noted that for almost all types of cluster analysis there are also fuzzy cluster analyses. Here, as described above, no clear assignment is made, but degrees of membership are determined. For an analysis, these usually have to be converted into a clear assignment. However, the explicit representation of fuzziness allows special insights that are obscured by non-hierarchical cluster analyses. In particular, the fuzzy cluster analyses already contain a quality criterion for the possible clusters. This brings us to the topic of validating the clusters and the classifications or cluster solutions.

Cluster analysis are offering the best possible classification structure for a given data set and and the properties of the classification structure defined with the method. If we have chosen the method correctly, this is the best result for a specific research objective. This does not mean, that the results are good. The results must be evaluated respectively validated. Two concepts of validation have to be distinguished, the internal and the external validation. The internal validation is testing how likely it is that the clustering structure is mapping a data inherent structure while the external validation tests the likeliness of the clustering structure mapping the ontic structure existing in the real world. So, in a certain sense the internal validation test if the classification structure is correct and the external validation tests if the result is meaningful.

The external validation uses one or several variables that are known to be relevant for our classification and correlates the classification result with these variables. The internal validation is generally based on two dimensions, the precision and the correctness. Correctness means that mean distance to the target point and precision the variance of values. In the context of classification we are rather using the terms compactness and separation. A class is compact if all objects described as points in the feature space are near the cluster centre and hence have a small variance. The separation is high, if the empty space between the clusters in the the feature space is large.

In practice, there are many validation key numbers, most a combination of separation and compactness (Coraggio2023; Everitt2011; Milligan1981; Milligan1996; Ullmann2022). One of the most helpful ones is the silhouette (Kaufman1990; Rousseeuw1987). The silhouette calculates the minimum distance to a point in another cluster for each point and subtracts the average distance in the cluster. The value is divided by the maximum distance between the clusters. The silhouette can assume values between -1 and 1, with negative values indicating an overlap of the clusters.

Epistemological Result

At this point, we should shortly summarise the epistemological results. We have distinguished four main types of classification with specific epistemic potentials: sc1, sc2, ac1, ac2. These types are defined based on the categories, a priori, a posteriori, synthetic, and analytic. Each type has a specific field of application and specific research objectives to answer. Inside each type the methods are also specific for clearly defined research objectives. The clustering methods for instance are sensitive for different kinds of clusters. Applying several method and looking for an agreement of the results means that the research objective is not precisely formulated. Unfortunately, the suggestion to apply several methods and decide to believe in the results if they agree can be found in statistical textbooks. That is understandable because statistical text books are not dealing with specific research objectives and hence they can not offer help for finding the right method. But the advise is still wrong because multiple methods do not validate the results to answer one question but are answers to multiple questions. In any case a validation is required because the cluster analysis itself does not include a quality assessment but just provides the best result. Further more, the clustering method has to be chosen carefully (Hennig2016).

Discussion

Now that we have a rough understanding of classification, we should relate the concept of classification to that of typology. Firstly, it is important to stress that there is a generally accepted definition. The two are often used interchangeably in archaeology. In logic, types are derived from classes (Cohen1934; Marradi1990). Occasionally types are defined by prototypes and classes by diagnostic features. In the context of archaeology, I would like to define types as interpreted classes. At least since Montelius (Montelius1885), archaeological types have at least a chronological implication. Archaeological types are therefore not only developed for a specific purpose, but are also generally interpreted in a corresponding way and thus go beyond classes. Types are generally subject to the presumption of positive external validation. In other words we can say, that mere classifications just work with low level theories that are concerned with rather technical contents, typologies require high level theories that offer a sound basis to interpret the actual content of the types.

Classifications as well as typologies can form a hierarchy that is not only a hierarchical classification. The classical artefact types are compared with other classification levels such as features or entities that emerge from grouping artefact types (cultures etc.).

This leads us to the question, why the higher hierarchy levels such as cultures, that are defined as interaction groups (Nakoinz2013; Nakoinz2014) and not in ethnic categories, use artefact and structure types and not simply their original features. The answer is twofold. First, from the perspective of classification, the types already provide correlated features. So, it could be possible that all features are regularly distributed in space and time but that certain combinations on the object level are specific. In this sense, the step by step classification provides nested correlations and hence is able to map structures of a higher degree of complexity. Second, from the perspective of types, the types in contrast to the classes are already laden with interpretations. This interpretation-surplus makes the resulting types even richer in meaning and offer additional facets.

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These considerations make the statements on the next aspect, universal classifications and typologies rather self-evident. It is obvious, that one universal classification for all purposes is not possible because because each purpose has different requirements on the classification. For the typologies it is clear, that an universal one would be overladen with meaning and hence, under determined. Though, one can aim for a maximal reach of a classification and even typology, an universal one is just not possible.

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Finally, we turn to some challenges. Machine learning and artificial intelligence are very fashionable approaches these days. They use predefined classifications and just assign objects to these classes. The difference to the predefined classifications mentioned above is, that the classes are not defined using parameters and diagnostic features but by examples. The systems develop some 'rules' for assigning objects, though, not explicit. Machine learning is rather a workhorse for the fast assignments of classes in case we already possess a large number of examples. These approaches basically generate data by connecting objects and classes. The newly classified objects can be used for correlation analysis and similar approaches to generate new knowledge. Machine learning and artificial intelligence do not allow to generate new knowledge directly and in particular not on ontological structures. These approaches basically a priori classifications of type ac1 (synthetic) that use some other data and hence is the least exciting classification approach for research. It just allows to generate large amounts of classification data very fast. These approaches are addressed as challenges because it will be a main task of the coming years to integrate ai into research approaches in a way that they provide more than just data. This means that we need to put the questions in a right way and use ai as a heuristic. In other words, ai needs to become creative. A simple example can illustrate this idea. Let us assume that we have a chronological system and artefacts that are assigned to these phases, either precise or fuzzy. If we have a information about the classification of some objects that can act as training data, we can ask the ai system to classify the others. For this purpose, we have other approaches that are based on closed finds. Since we are not including closed finds, we would doubt the ai results but the system can detect patterns that we did not perceive in particular in large data. This could generate some chronological hypothesis that are based on empirical evidence and would challenge the traditional approaches. This could be useful because closed finds are not precise measurements of simultaneity. Simultane existing objects can occur together in closed finds but they also may not. We are usually trusting the other connections are correcting this connection gap. This is just a very primitive example for a non-standard use of ai methods and many more advanced have to be developed in the near future. Involving machine learning in a more creative way will multiply the potential of those techniques for archaeological interpretation.

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With the above example we entered the topic of archaeological chronotypology. The traditional methods mentioned are mainly types of seriation. Seriation, seems to loose importance due to scientific dating and the reasonable critique, that the input categories, types and graves for instance are problematic. Seriations using traditional typologies or even worse, the next typology at hand are a kind of blind flying through chronological evidence. Considering alternative classifications might be a much better solution and nowadays scientific dating provide the option to validate the results. Used in this way the chronologies and the typology of the best fit form the basis for social and historical interpretations of the content of the classifications. Turning around the traditional approach might open new perspectives to archaeology.

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Conclusion

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Classifications are neither an end in themselves nor an outdated research practice, because they have always been, and still are, at the heart of all research, because only classifications make efficient systems of statements possible. The outcome of any research depends on the classification used. However, there

is no universal classification that would meet all requirements. Classifications are a fundamental tool for investigating relationships of any kind, but they can also be used in certain situations to gain knowledge about real ontic structures. In any case, it is important that the specific method of classification is adapted to the research question, the data and the underlying theory, otherwise the research may yield sub-optimal results at best. Although a comprehensive methodological apparatus for the development and use of classifications already exists, there are still major challenges in some areas. These include current developments such as artificial intelligence, which offer great opportunities but also lead to superficial approaches to research design, as has often been observed in the past. It is therefore important to recognise classification as a tool that creates opportunities for knowledge, but also has limitations. Each research question requires a specific classification approach in order to provide an optimal basis for further analysis.

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